

MUSIC PROGRAMMING – RULE-BASED RANDOMIZATION OF MELODIC PATTERNS

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ABSTRACT

Computers have long been used for aiding musical composition in a number of possible ways. Some composers use mathematical models such as combinatorial systems, grammars, probabilities and fractals to create new pieces of music. Other systems apply standard Genetic Algorithm procedures for evolving musical materials such as melodies, rhythms, chords, and so on. This paper describes the programming of musical parameters (such as time signature, key, scale etc) that form recognizable random melodic patterns based on some basic rules music compositions. It will also demonstrate the use of high-level programming language, such as JAVA to realize musical and logical concepts to generate melodic patterns.

KEYWORDS: Sound, Music composition, melody, rhythm, algorithm, and programming.

INTRODUCTION

Music is the alternation of sound and silence. When musicians play instruments, sound is produced (as the sound-producing parts of the instruments vibrate/oscillate). These vibrations cause air molecules to displace one another in a systematic continuous flow, which moves away from its source. In the end, our ears perceive these air pressure fluctuations as sounds that are translated by our brains as music (Garba 2003).

Musically speaking, the sounds produced are musical notes and the silences/pauses between the notes are called rests. The musical notes and rests vary in duration. That is, a note could be played for a long or short time. Thus, in contemporary music, there are six types of notes – whole, half, quarter, eighth, sixteenth and thirty-second. For proper interpretation of notes/rests duration, a piece of music is divided into portions called measures (bars). Each measure is bounded by two bars – within which a fixed number of notes/rests are required (Garba 2003).

To determine the number of notes/rests in a measure, a time signature (also known as meter) is required. This is usually placed in front of a musical staff. The time signature is a fractional number written in front of any musical piece. The numerator indicates the number of beats in a measure, while the denominator specifies the type of note/rest assigned to one beat. There are so many types of meters, but the common [C] time signature is 4/4 (i.e. four beats in a measure, and each beat is a quarter note) (Garba 2003). See *Table I* for more details.

Table 1 Musical Notes and Rest

Note Type	Note symbol	Rest symbol	Number of Notes/Rests
Whole		16	
Half		8	
Quarter		4	
Eight		2	
Sixteenth		1	

The combinations of notes/rests of varying durations make up the musical element called rhythm. Rhythm determines the flow, the movement and the feel of the music. Melody, on the other hand, is concerned with change in pitches/tones of the notes through time.

Figure 1 Melodic Pattern

Figure 2 Rhythmic Pattern

When a note is played, the tone heard is made up of the fundamental and the harmonics. The fundamental frequency is the main or the predominant tone, while the harmonic (also known as overtone or the partial) are the exact whole number multiples of the fundamental create the instrumental distinction known as timbre (Garba 2003).

The notes played by musicians are symbolized (using alphabets) according to their fundamental frequencies. For instance, C0 note represents 16.352Hz [C1 = 32.703Hz, C4 = 261.63Hz]. The alphabet stands for the type of note while the number stands for the value of the octave.

An octave comprises of seven notes: A, B, C, D, E, F and G. That is, same note (for instance, C note) at different octaves is just the multiple of the octave 0. For instance, C1 = 2*C0. Furthermore, an addition of five semitones (A#, C#, D#, F# and G#) to the seven notes of the octave form the chromatic musical scale – consisting of A, A#, B, C, C#, D, D#, E, F, F#, G and G# (Llewellyn 2007).

Digitization of Musical Concepts

In order to program and realize the aforementioned musical concepts, a pattern-based sampling approach is first applied to discover algorithm to an extant musical piece to reveal patterns at various levels of abstraction (Conklin 2007). Therefore, these concepts must be logically expressed via the binary number system. The simple logic here is this: when a musician plays a note, the binary number is 1; and when he doesn't, the binary number is 0. Thus, using the common time signature [4/4], a measure will contain 16 binary digits (bits). This means that a whole note binary value will be 1000 0000 0000 0000. See *Table 2* for more details.

In the light of the above, the following rhythm will have a binary value of 1000100010101000 1010101010001000. Therefore, it means a measure can

produce up to 65,536 [2¹⁶] rhythmic patterns. Melodic patterns are created once each note is

Table 2 Binary Interpretation of Musical Notes/Rests

Note Type	Note Binary Value	Rest Binary Value
Whole	1000 0000 0000 0000	0000 0000 0000 0000
Half	1000 0000	0000 0000
Quarter	1000	0000
Eight	10	00
Sixteenth	1	0

assigned a pitch according to the scale. Note that a single rhythmic pattern could produce several melodies; in the same vein, a particular melodic pattern could be varied to produce new rhythms. However, one of the drawbacks of this binary representation of rhythms is that information such as the intensity/dynamics of each note is not taken into account. Nevertheless, this representation is still useful for the initial generation of rhythmic patterns (Marcelo, *et al.* 2007).

Table 3 Musical and Logical Parameters

	Parameter	Description	Remarks
1	Scale	Each scale contains specific number and types of notes. There are different types of scales: major, minor, Lydian, Dorian etc.	This paper is considering the major scale only.
2	Key (the tonic key)	It denotes the base note for the musical tune according to the scale chosen.	The notes to be played depend on the scale.
3	Number of bars/measures	A musical piece is normally made up of more than one measure.	This paper will use a maximum of two bars.
4	Tonic octave	It denotes the base octave	The following octaves are considered: 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6.
5	Octave range	It specifies the number of octaves within which a note is played.	Three octave ranges are used in this paper.
6	Instrument type	Describes the instrument to be played.	The keyboard is considered in this paper.
7	Meter	It denotes the time signature	The common meter [4/4] is used here.
8	Tempo	It describes how fast the musical piece would be played (i.e. how many beats per minute).	This paper is considering a non-standard tempo reading.
9	Volume	It denotes the dynamics of the musical piece – indicating how loud the entire musical piece would be.	The range of 20 values between -10dB and +10dB is considered.
10	Humanize	It determines the dynamics/accents of the notes.	Five levels are used here.
11	Density	It determines the ratio between the number of notes and rests.	Variable levels are considered.

Musical and Logical Parameters

To produce, synthesize or generate musical tunes, a lot of musical parameters and natural factors have to be put into consideration. See the following table (Table 3) for concise details about these parameters.

Figure 3 Sample Screenshot of Melody Randomizer.

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this paper, an application called Melody Randomizer has been developed (by the author using JAVA as programming paradigm). The following sections explain the algorithm of Melody Randomizer via code listings. This application is divided into three major parts: parameters settings, melody generation and melody previewing/playback.

Melody Generation

There are several methods of melody generation. According to (Cope 1991), (Dodge 1985), (Worral 2001) and (Xenakis 1971), it is possible to use mathematical models such as combinatorial systems, grammars, probabilities and fractals to create new pieces of music. Other systems apply standard Genetic Algorithm procedures for evolving musical materials such as melodies, rhythms, chords, and so on (Marcelo, *et al.* 2007). However, in this paper, melodies are generated based on rules governing the formation of musical scales.

Once the parameters have been set, the process of generating melody is initialized by creating the notes of the selected scale.

1. An array of the chromatic musical notes is created: `String chromaticMusicalNotes [] = {"A","A#","B","C","C#","D","D#","E","F","F#","G","G#"};`
2. From the array above, the default scale indexes are created. Note that this paper is only considering the major scale. The default scale of note A has the following indexes: `int A_major_scale_indexes [] = {0,2,4,5,7,9,11};`. In other words, the A major scale contains A, B, C#, D, E, F# and G# notes. Note that it is the interval [2, 2, 1, 2, 2, 2] between these indexes that establishes the rule for creating a major scale.

3. Now, based on the established rule above, the major scale indexes of the remaining scale notes created using the A major scale indexes as a reference point. For instance, to create the C major scale indexes, get the index of the tonic note of the C major scale. From the array of chromatic musical notes, the index of the tonic note of the C major scale is 3 (i.e. C note). Then C major scale indexes will be 0+3, 2+3, 4+3, 5+3, 7+3, 9+3 and 11+3. But note that the calculated index must not be greater than 11; otherwise, this formula: new index = (calculated index - 11)-1 is used. If for instance, the calculated index is 14, then the new index = (14-11)-1 = 2. Finally, the C major scales will be 3, 5, 7, 8, 10, 0 and 2.

4.

```
public int[] indexes(int tonicNoteIndex){
int major_scale_indexes [] = new int [A_major_scale_indexes.length];
int new_index = 0;
for(int i=0;i<7;i++){
int index = A_major_scale_indexes[i] + tonicNoteIndex;
if(index > 11){
new_index = (index - 11) - 1;
} //end if...
else{
new_index = index;
} //end else...
major_scale_indexes [i] = new_index;
} //end for i
return major_scale_indexes;
} //end method indexes...
```

Melody Preview

After generating the melody, each note needs to be played back. This is possible by: generating beeps from the soundcard; using the MIDI sound bank or using sampled audio sound bank. However, in order to avoid some technical intricacies, in this paper, the sampled audio bank (which contains notes in small wave files) is used. See the result of the programming in the screenshot below (Figure 3).

CONCLUSION

Computer programming provides an inevitable gateway to music synthesis. This makes the production of soundtracks, jingles, melodies for TV, radio, film and special occasions very cost effective; while it serves as a boost to creativity in music composition and a means of developing and discovering new complex musical concepts.

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